

Source: flores
ID: Abe_2007

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Barrangou_2002

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Braun-Breton_1981

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Campbell_1995

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

C

Source: flores
ID: Caso_1995

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Comeau_2005

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Doi_2003

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Duplessis_2001

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Gamage_2004

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Goodridge_2003

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

C

Source: flores
ID: Holmfeldt_2007

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Kankila_1994

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Langley_2003

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Meyer_unpub

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Miklic_2003

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Mizoguchi_2003

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Pantucek_1998

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Paterson_2010

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Quiberoni_2003

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Seed_2005

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

C

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Suttle_1993

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Wichels_1998

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

Source: flores
ID: Zinno_2010

A

B

Metric: NODF

C

Metric: NT

